

of each entry were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a 2-row plot, 2.5 m long. A local susceptible variety was planted around the nursery. TN1 was the susceptible check and W1263 was the resistant check. Leaffolder-damaged leaves from 10 randomly selected hills of each variety were counted at 60 and 75 d after transplanting. Percent damaged leaves was computed with the following formula to correct for the level of insect pressure, as indicated by the susceptible check.

$$\text{Corrected \% damage} =$$

$$\frac{\% \text{ damaged leaves in test entry}}{\% \text{ damaged leaves in susceptible check}} \times 100$$

The following criteria were used on the converted scores to place percent damaged leaves on a 1-9 scale.

Scale	Damaged leaves (%)
1	1- 10
3	11- 20
5	21- 35
7	36- 50
9	51-100

None of the tested entries were free of leaffolder infestation. However, the following entries scored 3: GEB24 (acc. no. 5909), IR9209-26-2-2-3, NR59, PTB33, TNAU9039-14, TNAU9227-1, UPR311-19-2-1, UPR82-1-7, 343-D.T., and W1263 (acc. no. 11057). BG12-1, BG367-3, BKNBR1030-51-1-1-2-1, BR220-1-1, IR13429-170-3, IR19575-85-2-2-3, Kaohsiung Sen Yu 204, OR100-25, TKM6, T2005, and X2-D.T. scored 5. The remaining entries were highly susceptible. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Selection for cold-tolerant rice varieties in Kashmir, India

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About 1.8 million ha of riceland in the north and northeast hills of India have cold air and water temperatures during the growing season. In Jammu and Kashmir, rice is grown on 236,000 ha. About 67% (161,000 ha) of that is in the Kashmir Valley, 1,500 to 2,285 m altitude at 33.25 to 35.25 °N and 74.25°E longitude. Under normal conditions the growing season for rice is 145 d at 1,500 to 1,650 m elevations and 135 d at 1,650 to 2,285 m.

Although the area planted to high yielding modern varieties is increasing, early-maturing, cold-tolerant, high yielding, disease-resistant varieties are needed for high rice production in the hills. Low-temperature injury afflicts the crop at different growth stages. Temperatures at the early seedling and late maturing stages are hardly sufficient to sustain crop growth, and recovery from cold injury at higher elevations is low and slow. Minimum and maximum temperatures at seedling stage (Apr-May) are 6.4 to 9.8°C and 19.9 to 25.0°C. At maturity stage (Sep-Oct) minimum temperatures

Cold-tolerant crosses selected in Kashmir, India.

Cross	Cold-tolerant entries selected (no.)
Jukoku/IET1444	16
IET1444/Jukoku	10
IET1444/Hayayuki	15
Reimei/IET1444	14
IET1444/Houyoku	2
IET1444/K78-13	9
Kalinga I/Joesan Tongil	7
Kalinga II/Lysingi	2
AC71/KN-IB-361-1-8-6-9	6
K17-6-1-1-1/Kn-IB-361-1-8-6-9	1
K17-9-1-1/IR28	1
K21-9-10-1/IR2053-521-1-2	1
K143/IR28/IET1444	1
IET1444/Niver	2

are 11.3 to 4.6°C, and 24.8 to 22.9°C are maximum.

Low temperatures and cold irrigation water limit rice growth at early seedling, reproductive, and ripening stages. Breeding programs have been intensified to incorporate the cold tolerance of local and Japanese cultures into desirable, high yielding varieties.

In Apr and May 1982, the Kashmir Valley had an unusually long, cold spring with minimum Apr and May temperatures averaging 6.7 and 9.1°C. Most presoaked and presprouted seeds of the commonly grown varieties in open seedbeds or direct-seeded plots died and seeding had to be repeated. Of 1,367 lines (comprising 14 cross com-

binations) screened, 87 entries had a cold tolerance score of 1 at early seedling stage (see table). Parameters used to select for cold tolerance were leaf color, vigor, and survival percentage. Entries with cold tolerance are being tested in other trials. □

Inheritance of rice leaf discoloration resulting from low temperature

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Cold temperature limits the adaptation and production potential of rice varieties in subtemperate and temperate regions. Cold causes seedling mortality, stunting, poor tillering, leaf discoloration, poor panicle exertion, spikelet degeneration, and spikelet sterility. We studied the inheritance of leaf discoloration as affected by low temperatures.

We crossed Pratao, a cold-tolerant variety with a leaf discoloration score of 3, and IR8, a cold-susceptible variety with a leaf discoloration score of 7-9 and scored 20 F₁ plants and 10 plants of each parent in 1981. The F₁s had moderate leaf discoloration (a score of 5).

In 1982 wet season, F₁s of the cross and the parents were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing. Planting dates were

2. Waveforms recorded during GLH feeding on susceptible TN1 (top) and resistant ASD7 (bottom) rice varieties using an electronic monitoring device, IIRI.

A fine (18 m μ), 5-cm-long gold wire was attached to the dorsum of an 8- to 10-h-old GLH female by silver paint. The insect was starved for 2 h and then placed on the leaf blade of a 30-d-old susceptible TN1 or resistant ASD7 rice plant. The gold wire was connected to the negative input terminal of a D. C. chart recorder. The voltage source was two 1.5 V D. C. batteries connected in a series. The

positive battery terminal was connected with the plant roots through aluminum foil and moistened filter paper (Fig. 1). The negative battery terminal was connected with the positive input terminal of the chart recorder. GLH feeding activity was monitored for 180 min at a chart speed of 1.5 cm/min.

The waveforms recorded for GLH showed distinct differences in the feeding

activity on susceptible and resistant plants (Fig. 2). On susceptible TN1, the GLH probed readily and ingested for longer durations from the phloem (Pi), although initially the insect also sucked small amounts of xylem sap (Xi). On resistant ASD7, the insect made brief and repeated probes followed by salivation and feeding mainly from the xylem. □

Yield losses of a susceptible rice variety to brown planthopper (BPH) in Korea

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We evaluated rice yield losses to BPH of susceptible and resistant rice varieties in fields in southern Korea. Susceptible

varieties were Sumjinbyeo (japonica) and Milyang 23 (Tongil hybrid). Cheongcheongbyeo, with the *Bph 1* gene for resistance, was the check variety.

Seedlings were transplanted in early Jun and grown using traditional cultural practices without insecticide application. The BPH population was recorded 55, 70, and 90 d after transplanting. Yields of each variety were compared with that of an insecticide-sprayed plot.

Sumjinbyeo and Milyang 23 had a large BPH population, but infestation on Cheongcheongbyeo remained low. Yield losses were 29.4% for Sumjinbyeo and 19.1% for Milyang 23 (see table). BPH did not affect Cheongcheongbyeo yield. □

Yield losses of BPH-susceptible and resistant rice varieties, Suweon, Korea.^a

Variety	Reaction to BPH	Insects/plant			Days to hopperburn		yield (t/ha)		Yield loss %
		55 DI	70 DI	90 DI	Initial	Complete	Insecticide free	Insecticide treated	
Sumjinbyeo (japonica)	S	0.4	47.1	503.4	99	105	4.1	5.8	29.4
Milyang 23 (tongil hybrid)	S	0.1	12.8	500.7	101	108	5.4	6.6	19.1
Cheongcheongbyeo	R	0.0	0.3	8.7	—	—	6.0	6.0	0.0

^aAv for 3 replications. DT = days after transplanting.

Field resistance to rice leaffolder

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Leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* is a major rice pest in the hilly region of U.P. Infestation from Aug to Oct peaks in Sep. We screened rice genotypes to identify sources of resistance.

Thirty-one entries for screening from different countries were received from IRRI. They were field screened in 1982 wet season. Forty-five-day-old seedlings